

Vol. 1, No. 1 |

Spring 1987

Banko Janakari

The title we have chosen is the outcome of much discussion. It means 'information about forests'. There was general agreement that a Nepali title should be used, and one with something like this meaning had majority support. The final choice was sug-

gested by Mr E.K. Sharma, Chief of the Forest Survey and Research Office. The transliteration does not distinguish between the short (first and third) and long (second and fourth) 'a' but apart from that it gives a reasonable idea of the pronunciation.

The written word

Our new journal is intended to serve several purposes. It should make available, and put on record, any new findings from forestry research in Nepal. It should also draw attention to relevant information coming in from elsewhere. We hope it can also convey 'news' of various kinds, that will interest anyone concerned with forestry in this part of the world. Its columns will be open to anyone with ideas and opinions about Nepalese forestry and what can be done to improve things.

Our readers and contributors may be seen to fall into two main groups: trained Nepali forest officers and technicians, and the large number of foreigners here who have a connection with forestry. In fact we think their needs are very much the same, except for one important difference; the former group would obviously prefer to see some of the journal's contents written in Nepali. We are working on this, but frankly, we don't know how much can be done. Our enquiries so far have largely served to make us aware of the manifold difficulties of producing work of this kind in Nepali.

We have no illusions about the superior value of the printed word. We

know very well that new ideas are spread around in a multiplicity of ways, most of which involve the spoken word. Practical demonstrations and 'hands-on' training are of primordial importance. For the recording of scientific findings, computerized databases are rapidly developing. Nevertheless, the written word does have its place in the scheme of things. On the one hand, it should reach more people more quickly than any other medium currently available in Nepal. On the other hand, it provides a record that is permanent, convenient and can be widely disseminated at relatively little cost.

Our precursor, 'NEFTIB' (Nepal Forestry Technical Information Bulletin) did a good job, and seems to have been widely appreciated. As a scientific record, it has already proved its worth. We hope that with the new resources now available to us we can do something even better. The size and the frequency of issue, as well as the quality of this journal, however, are not completely under the control of the Editor. They will depend very much on the response of the scientific forestry community, and other interested parties, in Nepal. Please send your contributions and your comments.

On not planting trees

It is not difficult to gather a great variety of views about forestry in Nepal. It is common ground that forestry is of great importance to the country, and that all is not well at the present time. We think we can detect, over the last few years, widespread acceptance of some basic ideas which at one time did not seem quite so obvious as they do now. The prime importance of 'community forestry' is the new orthodoxy, and it is being realized that this means giving village communities real control of the forests that are important to them. At the technical level, it is now generally understood that the use of trees for fodder is not simply a destructive practice, to be deplored if it cannot be suppressed, but a vital part of the Nepalese rural economy.

As to what needs to be done, we find an almost universal, deep-seated belief that the answer is: plant more trees. This is not only the 'lay' opinion. Even in the Forest Research and Information Centre itself much effort has gone into nursery and plantation work, and into producing the Manual of afforestation in Nepal, by J.K. Jackson. It is true that this manual has a short section on 'alternatives to plantations'. It also has some important comments in its notes on certain species, pointing out that the need is not to plant them, but to protect and manage the natural stands. There is a considerable danger, however, that these words of wisdom will have little effect, and that those who take the practical decisions will continue to put most of their effort into tree planting. It is difficult to

convince people that they ought to be suspicious of tree planting, but the truth is that it is all too often the 'busy' solution, adopted by those who want to be seen to be doing something.

In trying to pick out what is truly of most importance to Nepalese forestry, we think it is best encapsulated in the slogan: better management! It is after all a basic tenet of scientific forestry that productivity depends on the maintenance of an adequate growing stock, and there is nothing obscure about the idea that if forests are overcut they will produce less and less. To translate this very simple idea into a recipe for the rehabilitation of Nepal's natural forests is another matter - but we think that the effort must be the central concern of all the agencies that are engaged in the struggle against forest destruction.

As always, of course, extreme simplifications need qualifying. Jackson's book itself sets out the reasons why planting is sometimes the right answer, and certainly when it is done it should be done well, now with the benefit of the 'Manual'. A companion volume, on the management of natural forests in Nepal, will be a far more difficult undertaking; indeed it is not easy to see where sources for it can be found. Research in forest management (meaning essentially control of cutting, lopping, grazing, etc.) is at the beginning of the road in Nepal. We hope we can be instrumental in gathering together any experiences or observations that have a bearing on this crucial matter.

